

Characterization and Expression Analysis of the Calmodulin Protein, CAM2, in *Arabidopsis Thaliana*

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Abstract:- Calmodulin is an intermediate calcium binding receptor messenger protein expressed in every eukaryotic cells. This is a very important factor in the *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Characterization and expression analysis of CAM2 were conducted to obtain important information of its function and regulation control under several stress condition. The study included ePlant heat map representation data, GO and KEGG analysis pathway interpretation. ePlant data gives us the insights of various tissue specific and cellular localization through heat map data. GO analysis data gives us inputs about molecular function, biological processes and cellular components. KEGG pathway analysis data represents how CAM2 expresses over any stress condition, how it is related with various conserved signalling pathways. Overall, these findings give us the answer that how each and every, environmental factors are connected with each other and how these organisms act upon certain environmental factors. The one of the most important findings from this characterization and expression analysis were, CAM2 is very important to response to several biotic factors such as pathogen interaction. CAM2 is highly responsible for the growth of mature pollen of *Arabidopsis thaliana*.

Keywords:- CAM2, *Arabidopsis Thaliana*, Gene Expression, Biotic Stress, Translation, Expression Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the human body or plant body if any organs are doing anything that is possible because of protein. Proteins are the main source of us doing any function, or the trees growing, giving us fruits, flowers each and everything. But what are these proteins? So, the proteins are the polymer of amino acids. Now to understand proteins we need to understand what amino acids are, an overview. They are nothing but a chemical compound consisting of both carboxyl (-COOH) and amino (-NH₃) groups. There are 20 different types of amino acids present in our environment. Proteins are being made by joining several simple neighbouring amino acids. Proteins have different structures - primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary (Meister, 2012).

These structures have several other subcategories also. A little misfolding in these protein structures can cause a huge amount of effect on the products. Proteins act as the backbone of every species on this planet. So it is very important to study the proteins functions, folding, characteristics and everything (Wilson, 2002). But why are we talking about proteins here? So, there are some proteins in the plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*, a very known model organism in plants which is CAM2, protein id – PODH97, consisting 149 amino acids, mass of 16'820 Da. It is a ubiquitous calcium binding protein. It works as a calcium signal translator into the appropriate cells of A. thaliana. So, calcium is a very important messenger for various functions such as biotic-abiotic stimuli, including pathogens, phytohormones, cold, heat, touch, drought etc (Laura Luoni, 2006). In *Arabidopsis thaliana* there are in total 7 CAM genes are there (Elizabeth McCormack, 2003).

Regulation of gene and protein expression is a very important factor in order to make things work inside the cell. Transcription: initial stage of gene expression is making RNA from DNA with the help of transcription. By modifying or regulating the transcription procedure it is possible to regulate the gene expression. Several environmental factors can influence the activity of many transcription factors. Post transcription: After producing various RNA molecules some post transcriptional modifications happen, that regulate the amounts of proteins from the RNA. For example, alternative splicing, where inclusion of exons or excluding happens, resulting in the amount or different types of protein formation. Translation regulation: mRNA converts into protein in the translation process. It happens with many steps including initiation, elongation, and termination. Post translational modifications: After protein synthesis, this process can regulate function of the proteins and their stability. Modifications including methylation, acetylation, glycosylation etc lead to the specific functions of various proteins (Theresa Phillips, 2008).

The regulation of gene and proteins leads to various expression/ adaptation among organisms – Expeditious response- In response to the environmental factor gene expression can be altered within the organism, factors such as temperature, stress, hormones etc may affect the gene expression. Calibrate gene expression – Gene expression can be adjusted according to the need in the specific

to shape three dimensional structures of proteins. The 3D structure of protein will metabolize. Then primary metabolism takes place. That 3D structure leads to cell signalling cascades, because proteins are the major part behind the cell signalling procedure. This 3D structure will make large protein networks. The 3D structure will lead to subcellular localization means those structures will go to different parts inside the cells. Then the 3D structure will also lead to localize itself in other part of the organism. After primary metabolism of proteins, it will continue to secondary metabolism. This whole process will altogether influence the organism's phenotype or the organism's response to the outer world (JamieWaese, 2017).

➤ *Model Organism*

Model organisms are the most requisite tool in the field of scientific research. No biological study would have been complete without any model organism. These organisms are chosen based on their easy availability, small genome, inexpensive to grow, high transformation efficiency, well characterized genetics. These all advantages help researchers to grow and test these organisms for various research purposes. These model organisms let researchers complete big experiments with large scale data, such as phenotypic assays, determination of biochemical pathways. Model organisms let them cultured in huge numbers and study for future inspections (Ankeny, 2020).

➤ *Arabidopsis: The model organism in plants*

Arabidopsis thaliana is a flowering plant, known as thale cress. It has become a very useful model organism to complete scientific study. The reason behind this is –

- Easy and inexpensive to grow and produces many seeds. They can be grown within very small space, such as growth chambers or rooms, making it easily available for studies. Also, they can be grown on agar plates or small pots, making it easier to handle anytime.
- *Arabidopsis thaliana* has a relatively small genome as compared to other plants making it easier to study more about this plant.
- A rapid life cycle of about 6 - 8 weeks from seed to seed makes it easier to study quick experiments, and study multiple generations in a relatively short time than other plants.
- It has high transformation efficiency, which means the efficiency to introduce foreign DNA in its genome. Because *Arabidopsis* has high regeneration efficiency it is very advantageous to introduce foreign DNA and test multiple patterns and complex pathways.
- *Arabidopsis* having approximately 125 million base pairs let this become the first completely sequenced genome, which has helped researchers with high amounts of genetic data, comprehensive gene maps, genetic variations, expression of genes. Forward genetic screens allow researchers to analyse large amounts of *Arabidopsis* mutants, which ultimately let us study many complex biochemical pathways.

All these advantages make *Arabidopsis thaliana* the best possible model organism in order to carry out many unsolved mysteries of this nature (Stefanie Wienkoop, 2010).

➤ *Gene Expression Analysis*

Genes are the backbone of our whole system. They are encoded with several proteins. Proteins are the result of those genes. We cannot understand the backbone of genes by simply just looking at them. We need to analyze each one of them with proper procedure. But why do we need to study the backbones and the functions of those genes?

By analysing genes we can determine the works, the functions it does for everything inside an animal or plant biological system. So long story short, to study the transcription process of genes we need to analyse its expression in the way it is expressed or in simple language the anatomy of the backbone of those genes, which is known as gene expression analysis (Winzeler, 2000).

➤ *Transcript Analysis*

Transcript analysis is a scientific approach by which scientists analyse the protein coding genes which are mRNAs. As stated earlier they are the backbones of these proteins which make a whole long gene which are responsible for various functions of many biological systems (Kornelia Polyak, 2003).

➤ *Use of Gene Expression/ Transcript Analysis in Understanding the Life Process*

We all have the same genes inside our body. The only difference is the way they are expressing themselves inside the body of a human or plant. Gene expression/ transcript analysis helps researchers understand new unidentified functions of some genes. Basically it helps in understanding the relationship between gene expression profiles and cellular organism phenotypes (Cycle, 2009).

➤ *Information from Gene Expression/ Transcript Analysis*

Analysing transcripts or gene expression studies gives us that the codons present inside the genes are responsible for their respective works. It helps us understand which codons are doing which functions or works inside the cell.

It gives the genetic information for any given species and if we are analysing an mRNA it will show us the codons that have been used to make the whole thing, from that we can see the functions or characteristics of that particular codon. That is how it helps in understanding gene function (Volgin, 2014).

➤ *How does it help in Understanding Gene Function?*

Gene expression analysis helps in understanding many unknown diseases and how to prevent them. By understanding gene function it becomes really easy decoding cellular functions which are unknown (Alberts B, 2002).

➤ *Different ways of Studying Gene Expression*

There are many ways for studying gene expression, which are northern blot, real time PCR, DNA microarray (Yongzeng Ding, 2007).

➤ *To Understand the Results of Gene Expression: Heat Map Representation of Data*

Heat map is a two-dimensional representation of data with various colours. The values are represented with colours to understand large scale data for eg; gene expression data better. In short within heat map there will be various colours, so for example there's a protein which is responsible for suppose the root division of *A. thaliana* so this will be represented by dark colours for the root division part which means it is expressing or the protein is upregulated at that particular area of the plant.

Light colours or no colours will be shown for that particular protein for the division of shoot, that light or no colour will make people understand that for those parts of the plant the protein is not expressing means it is downregulated there. Some other proteins are responsible for the shoot division of *A. thaliana*. So that's how we can easily understand by just looking at the heat map representation (Ziv Bar-Joseph, 2012).

➤ *Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI)*

Protein is everywhere and the most interesting thing is to understand how these proteins function or do their respective jobs, so to understand that we first need to understand how they interact with each other. So, the physical contacts between two or more proteins describe many biochemical pathways, cellular transports (Irene M.A Nooren, 2003).

➤ *The Significance of PPI in Cells*

To infer the protein function within the cell. There are many unidentified proteins that can be predicted on the evidence of their interaction with a protein whose function is already revealed. We need to understand PPI to understand

- Cell Signalling
- Cellular Transport
- Biochemical Pathways

➤ *Significance of Studying PPI*

Significance of studying PPI is that from studying PPI we can have an in-depth knowledge about the function of proteins within the cells and can identify unknown proteins. Some key point to study PPIs -

Cellular synchronization: Protein-protein interaction plays the most important role in order to continue the cellular functions. They carry out cellular responses. PPIs are responsible for gene expression, metabolism inside the cell, cell cycle continuation, and numerous other cellular functions. Various functions: Normally proteins act as combining with several other proteins and make a complex protein structure and then carry out many functions. If we are able to understand PPIs then it will be very easy to decode various complex pathways that determine the

functions by these proteins. Biomarker recognition: Altered protein-protein interaction may be related with various types of diseases or disease progression. Early identification of altered PPIs can aid the diseases. Network analysis & systems biology: PPIs are the building blocks of any complex cellular pathways. Understanding the core system of those biological functions can help scientists in understanding and decoding many complex central pathways, proteins origin etc (Nahid Safari-Alighiarloo, 2014).

➤ *Information about Protein from Protein - Protein Interaction*

There is a lot of information which can be understood by PPIs. Here is some information that we can get from PPIs-

Different types of interaction: Based on the mode of interaction, PPIs can be categorized, such as - Enzyme Substrate interaction: Specific enzymes interact with specific substrates in order to carry out some essential biochemical reactions. Receptor - ligand interaction: Specific receptors bind with specific ligands site to start many cell signals or other functions. Protein - DNA interaction: Proteins do bind with DNA, for example in transcription specific DNA gets bound with protein to regulate gene expression. Domain - domain interaction: Proteins have many domains within their structures. They can interact with those domains also resulting in various protein folding, changing in the functions.

Structural foundations: Proteins have several binding sites within it made of amino acid residues, which are complementary to each other. Such as hydrogen bonds, van der Waals interaction, hydrophobic bonds etc. The three-dimensional structure of proteins determines structural arrangements of these binding sites and strength of PPIs. PPI web: PPI networks contain a large number of interconnected connections which form a complex network within the cellular system. Analysing these PPIs give insights of these complex networks.

Studying Protein-protein interactions gives in depth knowledge about most crucial pathways which may help us get answers to many unsolved mysteries of several organisms.

➤ *Different Methods of Studying the PPI*

Yeast two hybrid methods are a method to understand and study protein - protein interaction. Suppose there is our protein of interest & we don't know which protein it'll interact with & what are the interactions of the protein inside the cell. So to understand that easily we have yeast cells. Transcriptional activator protein for this promoter site bind region for this Yeast cell is made up of 2 different types of protein both having DNA binding domain (DBD) & their own interacting domain.

Now we have our target protein named BAIT and a binding domain named PREY. If this target protein (BAIT) can bind with binding protein (PREY) then they can make an activated transcriptional activator complex. It will make a

signal to the cell to start the transcription of the desired gene, leading to production of the particular desired protein. Basically if these two (BAIT & PREY) make dimer receptor proteins then we can understand if one protein is interacting with another (Bram Stynen, 2012).

- *Protein Microarray Method -*

Protein microarray or protein chip is another type of method by which we can easily understand protein-protein interaction. It is a highly modern scientific costly method which gives best results about their function, their biochemical activities and other large scale data. This small chip is having cDNA or single stranded DNA attached to each of the round and small grooves that are created in the middle of the slide and we use a microarray to check the expression of different tissue at different time durations. We can determine if it is hybridizing using different dyes.

- ✓ Blocking agent
- ✓ Mask

We will incorporate diff nucleotides. Blocking agent is a chemical agent which once added to a groove will not bind to any specific nucleotide. But the blocking agent can be knocked off using a laser. We need to construct a DNA or a different nucleotide sequence into these grooves so that it forms a nucleotide chain.

Mask will cover the whole thing. There will be cover but there will be some portions which will be empty also. If there's a mask then no longer it will bind with any nucleotide sequence.

- 1st adding blocking agents
- 2nd addition of mask
- 3rd Exclude the blockers using lasers
- 4th addition of nucleotides
- Each time the nucleotides are added the mask will be changed & new mask will be placing there
- 5th new mask
- 6th removal of blocker using laser

Repeat this process until 20 to 25 nucleotide sequences in each of these small grooves.

Now extracting the DNA & making cDNA out of it & can extract RNA & cDNA from it.

We need to check the expression of a particular gene for the total number of RNA transcripts that are present inside the cell or to check the “transcriptome” that is present inside the cell (Markus F Templin, 2002).

- *GO (Gene Ontology) Analysis*

Gene ontology is a complete vocabulary composed of > 38 '000 precisely defined phrases called GO terms. Gene ontology knowledgebase is the world's largest source of information on the functions of genes. It is used for gene enrichment studies. Every set of gene has their specific GO number, by which it can be easily searched and discuss about their functionality.

- *Information we get from GO Analysis*

It mainly gives three types of information - Biological processes (BP), Cellular components (CP), Molecular functions (MF). With the help of a hierarchical representation of data we can understand the results of many complex pathways, biological functions.

- *Significance of GO Analysis*

With the help of Gene ontology, we can have a framework & set of concepts for describing the function of gene products from all organisms. It decreases the complexity level in understanding many important and complex biological processes (Matthew D Young, 2010).

- *KEGG Pathway Analysis*

Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes & Genomes. It is a collection of manually drawn pathway maps of large biochemical processes including much vital information related to the genes that do all the major functions in the biological system. There is numerous data present in the KEGG pathway analysis. But currently the best organized pathway is metabolism. This analysis mostly focuses on the network of gene products mostly proteins but some functional RNAs are also there (Junli Du, 2014).

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

- *Expression Analysis Studies (ePlant)*

ePlant is a data visualization tool for plant data. We used this website to harvest various heat map representation data of *Arabidopsis thaliana*.

- *Method*

- ✓ First, we need to open the ePlant website, and then we have to put the accession number of our gene of interest which is *CAM2*, AT2G41110 is the accession for this gene. We have to put this accession number in the field of “enter a gene name” part.
- ✓ Next, after the process begins, we will have several types of heat map data, we specifically selected various tissue specific data and cellular localization data to interpret (chmid et al., 2005).

- *Identification of Protein Interactors (BAR)*

This tool is used to identify which proteins are interacting with our protein of interest, *CAM2*. This tool gives us a interactor list to identify and study further.

- *Method*

- ✓ First, we need to open the BAR list of interactors website, then we have to put the accession number in the first pop up window.
- ✓ Now we have to select databases to query, and after that it will show us the results.
- ✓ From this we can download the results in our system. Thus we got the list of interactors of our protein of interest (<https://bar.utoronto.ca/interactions2>, n.d.).

➤ *Analysis of the Putative Function of CAM2 Protein through Study of Interactors*

To analyse the putative function of **CAM2** protein through interactors, we used two of the analytical methods that are Gene Ontology (GO) and KEGG pathway. To harvest the data we used DAVID Bioinformatics Resource tool.

• *Method for GO Analysis*

- ✓ First, we need to open the DAVID tool, then we have to paste the list of interactors which we previously harvested from BAR list of interactors.
- ✓ Then we have to select “ENSEMBL GENE ID” from the “identifier list”, scroll down and select “gene list”, submit.
- ✓ A window will open named “Annotation summary results”.
- ✓ We have to select from “Gene ontology” – “GOTERM_BP_DIRECT, GOTERM_CC_DIRECT, GOTERM_MF_DIRECT”. These are just to clarify to the website that we need only the biological processes, cellular components and molecular function data from this, and then scroll down and click on “functional annotation chart” and submit.
- ✓ A new tab will open with all the harvested data that will have the three types of data including BP, CC and MF.
- ✓ Now we have to make a table from this harvested data to plot the graphs.

• *Method for KEGG Pathway Analysis*

- ✓ Again, we have to go back to the window “Annotation summary results”.
- ✓ Click on “Pathways”.
- ✓ Select “KEGG”.
- ✓ Click on “functional annotation chart” and submit.
- ✓ Another new tab will open with the harvested data that will have the KEGG pathway results.
- ✓ We have to make another table from this data to plot the graph (Sherman BT, 2022).

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. *Expression Analysis Studies Data (ePlant)*

Gene expression analysis is the most crucial step to analyze the various parts of a plant or any organism where exactly how much the gene is expressed and what function it has for those particular parts of the plant. With the help of heat maps, we can easily understand in which part of the model organism *Arabidopsis thaliana* the gene of my interest which is *CAM2* is expressed more or less or has medium expression level.

➤ *Tissue Specific Response of CAM2: Pollen showed up Regulation of CAM2*

Fig 2 Tissue Specific Heat Map Representation of *CAM2* in *Arabidopsis Thaliana*

The very first leaves of the model organism *Arabidopsis thaliana* are known as Rosette. As we can observe from this heat map analysis of the model organism *Arabidopsis thaliana*, the gene *CAM2* is ubiquitously present. A significant data has been observed from the leaf, that is the gene expression was upregulated till 11, 12 stage, but it has shown downregulation at cauline and significant amount of downregulation at senescent stage. The value has been taken into consideration from 0 to 1493.1. Light yellow to bright red helped us understand better the expression of

CAM2 gene in every part of the plant. From this image we can see,

- The lowest level of *CAM2* expression is in the dry seed with level 9.05 expression of this gene in the dry seed.
- Then moving with gradual increase of expression of *CAM2* with levels 53.47 in imbibed seed.
- 8.12 in the vegetative rosette.
- Then upregulation in the Flower stage 9 with level 120.95

- Downregulation when the flower was in 10/11 form with level 83.83
- Again, gradual increase Flower stage 12 sepals with level 144.4
- Flower stage 15 with expression level 122.63

But the highest level of expression as seen in the image with red colour is of “mature pollen”, with the expression level of 1493.1. This upregulation of *CAM2* at mature pollen describes that it is highly needed for this plant at mature pollen stage to overcome various stress condition. Low expression throughout except at the stage of maturity of pollen. Here some level of upregulation of mature rosette

leaves also can be seen. Maybe they are essential for several important processes (including photosynthesis) that are active at the mature stage of the developing rosette leaves. It also indicates that the expression of *CAM2* protein is developmentally regulated in the same tissue (expressed at different levels at different developmental stages of the rosette leaves) (Schmid et al., Nature Genetics 37:501 and Nakabayashi et al., 2005, The Plant Journal, Vol 41:697., 2005).

➤ *Tissue Specific Stigma & Ovaries Response: Highly Upregulation of CAM2 at Pistil Tissue*

Fig 3 Tissue Specific Stigma & Ovaries Heat Map Representation of Data of *CAM2* in *Arabidopsis Thaliana*

The pistil tissue of *Arabidopsis thaliana* primarily consists of ovaries. In this heat map data the value has been taken into consideration are from 0 to 330.69. As we can observe, tissue of the ovaries is the part where *CAM2* has the highest amount of expression which is 330.69. The upper portion of this tissue has stigma tissue which has a slightly lesser amount of expression which is 164.96. This

expression concludes that in the pistil tissue *CAM2* was ubiquitously upregulated, indicating the fact that the plant needed the gene in order to function properly (Swanson, 2005).

➤ *Tissue Specific Embryo Development Response: Apical and Basal Tissue Showing Upregulation of CAM2*

Fig 4 Tissue Specific Embryo Development Heat Map Representation of Data of *CAM2* in *Arabidopsis Thaliana*

Arabidopsis being a dicotyledonous flowering plant, it has three stages of embryo development. In this slide the expression of the CAM2 gene in tissue specific embryo development has been shown. In this heat map data the value has been taken into consideration from 0 to 45.48. We can understand that the heart shaped upper cotyledons have the lowest amount of CAM2 gene expression of 14.93. The root part has an expression of 30.67. The basal part of the globular shaped one has an expression of about 29.43 and apical part has 31.8. The torpedo shaped cotyledons have expression of 18.6, the root has 29.1, the meristem has 30.28, the basal part has 39.15 and the apical part of torpedo

shaped has the highest amount of CAM2 expression which is 45.48. For the torpedo shaped embryo apical and basal part has the most upregulation of CAM2 because those parts needed CAM2 gene to get the shape and facilitate other function, whereas initially the gene showed low to moderate level of expression, may be because in those stress condition it was not possible for CAM2 to be expressed and facilitate other function (al. C. e., 2005).

➤ *Tissue Specific Pollen Germination Response: Significant Amount of CAM2 Expression Showing in Pollen*

Fig 5 Tissue Specific Pollen Germination Heat Map Representation of Data of CAM2 in Arabidopsis Thaliana

Here we can see three stages of pollen, which are in vitro germination for 30 minutes, dry pollen and 4 hours in vitro germinated pollen and pollen tubes after growth through stigma and style (pistil explants). In this heat map data the value has been taken into consideration from 0 to 962.46. Expression of CAM2 gene for 30 minutes in vitro incubation pollen is the lowest which is 629.04. Dry pollen

has an expression of 696.15. Whereas after 4 hours of in vitro germination the expression is 679.73. The pollen tubes harvested after growth through pistil explants have the highest amount of CAM2 expression of 962.46 (al, 2009).

➤ *Response to Biotic Stress*

Fig 6 Biotic Stress Elicitors Heat Map Representation of Data of CAM2 in Arabidopsis Thaliana

Stress elicitor is a chemical substance which is being used in this experiment to show how much the *CAM2* gene will get expressed in such a stress condition to fight against a foreign substance if introduced with *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Here scientists took a biotic stress elicitor, meaning they took a living organism and then extracted the chemical which can be used as a stress elicitor to continue the experiment. In this heat map representation of data, we can see where the value has been taken into consideration from 0 to 1065.05. In this experiment various biotic stress elicitors were used to see the expression of *CAM2*. We can observe from this heat map data that in the initial first hours the *CAM2* gene expression was significantly upregulated after introducing the stress elicitors, but at 4th hours, the gene expression is downregulated. We can conclude from

the data that, when the plant was introduced with biotic stress elicitors the expression of *CAM2* significantly decreases with time. If *CAM2* expression is downregulated at certain stress condition (for ex; here – at 4th hour when infused with bacterial derived) that indicates that this stress negatively affects the expression of the gene. Thus, it also impairs the functions associated with that gene in the plant processes. When in the 1st hour *CAM2* gene is upregulated at the stress condition of bacterial derived elicitor means plant need it to adapt to this new stress environment. *CAM2* gene is essential for plant to withstand this stress in the initial hours. It also indicates that this protection is not long-term, prolong biotic stress (al W. e., 2017).

➤ Response to Abiotic Stress

Fig 7 Abiotic Stress Elicitors Heat Map Representation of Data of *CAM2* in *Arabidopsis Thaliana*

Abiotic stress is the type of stress condition where several environmental factors are involved in order to observe the *CAM2* gene expression in various environmental stress conditions. As we can observe from the image, many different stress factors were chosen, like – first to get a brief comparison control has been taken, cold, osmotic, salt, drought, genotoxic, oxidative, UV-B, wounding, heat. The value has been taken into consideration from 0 to 608.77. As we can see from the heat map interpretation, the highly expressed *CAM2* in the shoot of the plant was because of UV-B stress in the 3rd hour which is the highest 608.77. A

very significant amount of upregulation of the gene can be observed at the 24th hour in the root part of the plant in the cold stress. Significant amounts of upregulation can be seen in the rosette leaves under UV-B stress at frequent hours of 0.5th, 1st and 3rd hour. And the downregulated expression can be seen in the stress wounding at 1st hour in the shoot. And for other stress factors, in different time scales less amount of expression has been seen. The expression of the *CAM2* gene in the root is quite similar or less for every hour with respect to different abiotic stress factors (al. K. e., 2007).

➤ *Light Dependent Response for Germination Caused by CAM2*

Fig 8 Germination Heat Map Representation of Data of CAM2 in Arabidopsis Thaliana

In the above slide it has been tested the germination of the plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*. We can observe from this heat map data that, *Arabidopsis* being a plant, in stratification the gene expression is downregulated for germination, but in light sources the upregulation is very significant. This observation concludes that *CAM2* is responsible for germination of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. In this heat map data the value has been taken into consideration from 0 to 68.85. First 48 hours it has been put in stratification. Where we can see that *CAM2* was expressed but in a very limited amount which is 0.91 to 13.99. Then the next day it was put in light for 48 hours. There we can

see a significant amount of *CAM2* expression in the first 24 hours in light and next 48 hours in light, which is 68.73 and 68.85 respectively. This data suggests that gene expression/transcription is controlled by light. There is a light regulation of *CAM2* gene which must be occurring by action of the transcription factors on the promoter of *CAM2* gene to positively regulate its expression. This also indicates that this gene may be a part of the cellular network that may have crucial role in greening process of the plants at early developmental stages (al. N. R., 2011).

➤ *Localization Response of Arabidopsis Thaliana Cell*

Fig 9 The Interactive Data Analysis Centre for Arabidopsis Subcellular Protein Locations.

Cells are the base of any organism. Cellular localization data is to understand that in the cell, where in the cell the *CAM2* protein is present. It is important to understand where the protein is localized in the cell of

Arabidopsis thaliana in order to achieve the correct analysis of the protein interacting with which type of signalling pathways, protein-protein interaction, cellular organization. In this heat map data representation, we can see the value

has been taken into consideration from 0 to 20. As the heat map data suggests mostly in the cytosol and nucleus the **CAM2** is present in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. **CAM2** is being localized at Mitochondrion, plastid, vacuole. And the rest of the cellular organelle does not have much **CAM2** protein present in there, depicting that those, organelle where **CAM2** has been found majorly need **CAM2** the most in order to carry out cellular functions, or they are involved

with major signalling pathways, but where it isn't found in much significant amount, it can be concluded that for those **CAM2** protein might not be that significant but cam3/5/7 might be needed the most for those organelle to carry out other important cellular functions (Hooper CM, 2017).

B. Identification of Protein Interactors (BAR)

Table 1 List of Interactors of **CAM2** Protein in *Arabidopsis Thaliana*

Serial No.	List of interactors	Description	Reference
a.	At1g51710	UBP6 ubiquitin-specific protease 6, majorly present in cytosol	BAR - PMID 15987637 BAR - BioGrid 467602
b.	At3g21630	LYSM RLK1 chitin elicitor receptor kinase 1, majorly present in plasma membrane	BAR - BioGrid 1173012 BAR - PMID 25036661
c.	At5g54590	CRLK1 Protein kinase superfamily protein, majorly present in ER and extracellular part	BAR - BioGrid 1108043 BAR - PMID 20724845
d.	At5g65930	ZWI kinesin-like calmodulin-binding protein (ZWICHEL), majorly present in plasma membrane	BAR - PMID 10531384
e.	At1g51500	WBC12 ABC-2 type transporter family protein, majorly present in plasma membrane	
f.	At2g46240	BAG6 BCL-2-associated athanogene 6, majorly present in nucleus	None
g.	At3g56800	CAM3 calmodulin 3, majorly present in vacuole	INTACT - PMID 15299147

➤ *From the Derived Data, we can see there are 7 Interactors that Interacts with our Protein of Interest CAM2.*

- Ubiquitin specific protease 6, (UBPs) are the most important for the selective proteolysis of cellular proteins. UBP interacts with **CAM2** in *Arabidopsis thaliana*.
- Chitin, is an integral part of fungal cells, plays a crucial role in plant immune responses in *Arabidopsis*. These interactions were found from Yeast two hybrid method.
- CRLK1 Protein kinase superfamily protein. Several studies regarding this protein's interaction with **CAM2** revealed that this protein is responsible for plant's response to abiotic stress such as chilling and freezing

temperature. These interactions were found from Yeast two hybrid method.

- ZWI kinesin-like calmodulin-binding protein (ZWICHEL), this protein interacts with **CAM2**. Results derived from Yeast two hybrid method.
- CAM3 is a calmodulin-Ca²⁺ complex. This bar list of interactor result suggests that it interacts with **CAM2**. It needs to be investigated if two diff calcium binding proteins also interact among themselves to relay down the calcium signalling pathways.

C. Analysis of the Putative Function of CAM2 Protein through Study of Interactors

➤ *GO (Gene Ontology) Analysis Molecular function (MF) Table and Graph*

Table 2 Molecular Function (CC) Table of Gene Ontology (GO)

Term ID	Molecular Function	No. of genes	% of genes
GO:0005509	Calcium ion binding	4	44.4
GO:0005516	Calmodulin binding	4	44.4
GO:0005515	Protein binding	8	88.9
GO:0005524	ATP binding	4	44.4
GO:0042803	Protein homodimerization activity	2	22.2

Fig 10 Gene Ontology (GO) Analysis of Genes Pathway Analysis of CAM2, Molecular Function (MF)

- GO:0005509: Calcium ion binding involved in regulation of cytosolic calcium ion concentration (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0005509>, n.d.).
 - GO:0005516 Calmodulin (calcium modulated protein) binding (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0005516>, n.d.).
 - GO:0005515: Binds with various kinds of proteins (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0005515>, n.d.).
 - GO:0005524: Binds with ATP (universally important enzyme) (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0005524>, n.d.).
 - GO:0042803: Protein homodimerization activity, binding to an identical protein to form a dimer (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0042803>, n.d.).
- *GO (Gene Ontology) Analysis Cellular Components (CC) Table and Graph*

Table 3 Cellular Components (CC) table of Gene Ontology (GO)

Term ID	Cellular components	No. of genes	% of genes
GO:0005874	Microtubule	4	44.4
GO:0000325	Plant-type vacuole	3	33.3
GO:0005886	Plasma membrane	4	44.4

Fig 11 Gene ontology (GO) analysis of genes pathway analysis of CAM2, Cellular components (CC)

- *GO:0005874: Microtubule, part of a microtubule cytoskeleton, that eventually help in cellular components (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0005874, n.d.).*
 - *GO:0000325: Associated with cellular component, plant type vacuole (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0000325, n.d.).*
 - *GO:0005886: Plasma membrane is a membrane that is a part of cellular periphery that is a cellular anatomical entity, part of the cellular component (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0005886, n.d.).*
- *GO (Gene Ontology) Analysis Biological Processes (BP) Table*

Table 4 Biological Processes (BP) table of Gene Ontology (GO)

Term ID	Biological Processes	No. of genes	% of genes
GO:0019722	Calcium-mediated signalling	3	33.3
GO:0009846	Pollen germination	2	22.2

- *GO:0019722: Calcium mediated signalling is a second messenger mediated signalling, that is intracellular signal transduction, part of cell communication, occurs in intracellular anatomical structure. Cellular signalling is the regulation of biological process, that is a response to stimulus, which finally make the whole biological process (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0019722, n.d.).*
 - *GO:0009846: Pollen germination is a part of pollination, which is a reproductive process, which finally make a multicellular organism, which finally make it a biological process (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/QuickGO/GTerm?id=GO:0009846, n.d.).*
- *KEGG Pathway Analysis Table and graph*

Table 5 KEGG Pathway Analysis Table

Term	Gene Count	% of genes
Plant pathogen interaction	4	44.4
Phosphatidylinositol signalling system	3	33.3
MAPK signalling pathway - plant	3	33.3

Fig 12 Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes and Genomes (GO) Pathway Analysis of CAM2

- *Plant pathogen interaction: Data derived from several researches suggested that CAM2 is involved in plant pathogen interaction. CAM2 expression upregulates when interacts with certain stress factors. From the ePlant data of Biotic stress factors (Fig. 9) of CAM2 regulation it can be concluded that this protein is very crucial for Arabidopsis thaliana to fight against certain pathogen response (DAVID Annotation Tool, n.d.).*
- *Phosphatidylinositol signalling system: Data derived from several researches suggested that CAM2 is involved in phosphatidylinositol signalling system (DAVID Annotation Tool, n.d.).*
- *MAPK signalling pathway – plant: Data derived from several researches suggested that CAM2 is involved in MAPK signalling pathway (DAVID Annotation Tool, n.d.).*

V. CONCLUSION

The characterization and expression analysis of *CAM2* in *Arabidopsis thaliana* have been done to understand various important factors regarding *CAM2* of this study were to perform expression analysis of *CAM2* in *Arabidopsis thaliana* using heat map representation data, identify *CAM2* interactor genes and analyze their expression, and conduct Gene Ontology (GO) and KEGG pathway enrichment analysis of the *CAM2* interacting proteins. The specific focus on *CAM2* was driven by the need to explore its role and significance in plant biology. Through a comprehensive analysis, we adopted various approaches to unravel novel insights associated with *CAM2*. All the information presented here about *CAM2* is derived from in silico studies.

The *Arabidopsis* genome has 7 CAM genes, which encode for 4 highly conserved isoforms: *CAM1/ CAM4*, *CAM2/ CAM3/ CAM5*, *CAM6* and *CAM7* (Elizabeth McCormack Y.-C. T., 2005). I started my approach by studying and analyzing the *CAM2* gene of *Arabidopsis thaliana* because it has remarkable ubiquitous expressions in the plant, and it may help study and reveal more aspects about *CAM2* for future research.

The expression analysis study suggested that *CAM2* is ubiquitously present in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. The most significant expression can be seen at the time of pollen germination and the mature pollen stage. The upregulation of *CAM2* suggests that at the time of pollen germination, *CAM2* is highly needed by the plant to overcome several stress factors in order to achieve a mature pollen, which also includes photosynthesis.

For the biotic stress factor, a significant amount of upregulation can be seen at the very 1st hour of testing using the stress elicitors (using bacterial derived chemicals), indicating that plants need *CAM2* to adapt to this new environment. But in the 4th hour of the test, they also found downregulation of *CAM2* indicating that this stress negatively affects the expression of the gene, thus impairing the functions associated with that gene in that procedure. Thus concludes the fact that plants need *CAM2* to adopt the new stress, but the effect is not prolonged. This data also suggests that, after adapting to the new stress condition, the plant might need any other gene to function.

The *CAM2* interactor findings, guided by the in silico studies, suggested that *CAM2* has seven interactors. UBP, an important factor responsible for plants selective proteolysis, interacts with *CAM2*, which suggests that *CAM2* is also responsible for plants selective proteolysis. The CRL1 protein kinase does interact with *CAM2*, which ultimately is responsible for the plant's response to several abiotic stresses such as freezing, chilling temperatures. These data suggest *CAM2* is an important intermediate factor in sensing and responding to abiotic stress. The protein chitin elicitor is an integral part of fungal cells, plays a crucial role in plant immune responses in *Arabidopsis*, and interacts with *CAM2*. This data suggests that *CAM2* is an important intermediate factor in sensing and responding

to biotic stress. *CAM2* interacts with *CAM3* of *Arabidopsis thaliana*, but further research and investigation are needed to know more about these two proteins interactions and whether two different calcium binding proteins also interact among themselves to relay calcium signaling pathways.

The GO analysis and KEGG analysis data suggest some more important findings about *CAM2*. From GO analysis of in silico data, we have found that it has five data points that suggest *CAM2* has some important functions in molecular function, including calcium binding, calmodulin binding, protein homodimerization activity, and protein and ATP binding. It has three data points that suggest its importance in cellular components, including the plasma membrane, plant-type vacuole, and microtubule. 2 data suggesting the fact that *CAM2* has importance in biological processes including pollen germination and calcium-mediated signaling, which is vastly known that calcium is the main component when talking about CAMs (Iris Steinebrunner, 2000). KEGG analysis data suggests *CAM2* interaction in complex biochemical pathways, including plant-pathogen interaction, the phosphatidylinositol signaling system, and the MAPK signaling pathway.

In conclusion, the characterization and expression analysis study of *CAM2* in *Arabidopsis thaliana* has provided some useful and important insights. Future research can be done, and it might focus on understanding the interaction between *CAM2* and *CAM3*, and other important molecular functions and signaling pathways associated with *CAM2* to further elucidate its function and potential role in biotic and abiotic stress factors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Siddhartha Dutta, for his invaluable guidance and unwavering support throughout the thesis writing process of my research on the characterization and expression analysis of the calmodulin protein, *CAM2*, in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Dr. Dutta's expertise in the field of plant molecular biology and his dedication to scientific research have been instrumental in shaping the direction and scope of my thesis. His profound knowledge, insightful suggestions, and critical feedback have greatly enriched my understanding of the subject matter.

I am especially grateful for Dr. Dutta's patience and encouragement, which have instilled in me a sense of confidence and motivation to overcome challenges encountered during the research. His open-door policy and willingness to devote time to discussions and brainstorming sessions have been invaluable in refining my ideas and enhancing the quality of my work. His mentorship has not only nurtured my academic growth but has also inspired me to pursue excellence in scientific research. I extend my heartfelt

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